

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7125780

IMPACT OF INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION 4.0 TO THE VIETNAMESE CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Received: 31/08/2022

Accepted: 10/10/2022

ABSTRACT

In the process of development, if the economy is considered as the material foundation of society, meeting material needs, then culture is the spiritual foundation of society, meeting the spiritual needs of people and society. The development of each country, economy, and culture are interrelated, in which culture covers all aspects of social activities; not only governs influence but also can regulate the development of society. Currently, the fourth industrial revolution has had a profound impact on all areas of socio-economic life in Vietnam, including culture. To take advantage of opportunities and minimize negative impacts, countries need to assess the impact of this revolution comprehensively, including the impact on culture, thereby reorienting development strategies, focusing on investing in science and technology, and at the same time having policies to preserve and promote national cultural values is one of the most essential tasks of the current Vietnamese revolution.

KEYWORDS: opportunities, challenges, Industrial Revolution 4.0, cultural development, Vietnam

1. INTRODUCTION

The world is undergoing a process of globalization with the strong development of the Industrial Revolution 4.0¹, which is rapidly increasing the relationship between nations and peoples in many aspects of social life, including culture. On the one hand, these processes make ethnic cultures have conditions to exchange, learn and acclimate each other, enrich and enhance cultures of ethnic groups, and at the same time develop and enrich the culture of the common culture of all mankind. On the other hand, these processes also pose to countries the risk of the fading of national cultural values, the purely deviant promotion of scientific, technical, and technological civilization, a way of life that pursues trivial material interests and values, neglect or disregard of national cultural values, etc. Once the above risks commonly take place, it will not only lead to monotony and poverty of ethnic cultures, but also monotony and poverty of the common culture of all mankind; not only does it reduce the formation and development of an individual's personality, but also it reduces the ability, true meaning as well as harmony, balance, and sustainability in the development of society. Vietnam is a multi-nationality country of 54 ethnic groups with many beautiful traditions, diversity and inclusion (Bizivietnam, 2021). Due to the special location, Vietnam's traffic culture has been rich and strong every year especially. During the period of the fourth industrial revolution, Vietnamese culture and lifestyle continued to change. However, it is not only the transformation due to continued transformation from other cultures, but more complex is the automatic change from within the content of the culture in both the direction of activity and focus when it deviates from the standardization of values.

Culture becomes a meaningful issue not only for the development of each individual but also it has a profound and broad social meaning, has an important position, and has a profound influence on all aspects of life, relationships and activities. Therefore, studying the impact of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 on culture has practical significance for countries, peoples, and humanity today.

The article focuses for first time on analysing the impacts and challenges of the industrial revolution 4.0 on cultural development in Vietnam and proposes some solutions to take advantage of opportunities and overcome challenges of this "cultural revolution"

to develop Vietnamese culture to meet the current requirements of international integration and digital transformation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on Industrial Revolution 4.0: The work of Klaus Schwab, "The Fourth Industrial Revolution" the author presents contents such as revolution the fourth industrial network, its emergence, and its profound changes; and the impacts of Industrial Revolution 4.0 on all areas of social life, especially for the world labor market (Klaus, 2018). Along with this research direction, the book "Industrial Revolution 4.0 - Problems posed for socio-economic development and international integration of Vietnam" presented the most fundamental issues about the birth history of the industrial revolutions; industrial trends of the IR 4.0; opportunities, challenges, and requirements of the IR 4.0 for socio-economic development in general as well as for the labour market in Vietnam. From the analysis of the impact of IR 4.0, the author has given directions and solutions to build and develop the capacity to innovate and think creatively to take advantage of opportunities and overcome the challenges of IR 4.0 in Vietnam in the coming time (Hoa, 2017).

In addition, Phil & Christen (2018) in their work on the *intelligentsia in the face of the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0*, note that: "Technology has the potential to free us from the toil or destruction of livelihoods, and the choices that governments make, and the company offers often determines the difference" (Phil & Christen, 2018). Tri et al, (2021) commented that: "The Industrial Revolution 4.0 with its rapid development speed and profound impacts on all areas of the social life of each country if left behind of this revolution, the backward development is also inevitable. On the contrary, if you make good use of the advantages of this revolution, the opportunities are huge".

Research on cultural development: From the 19th century onwards, culture became the object of research not only in cultology but also in many social sciences and humanities such as philosophy, ethnology, anthropology. Huntington, (2000) mentioned a number of issues about national culture and factors to recognize the cultural identity of each country, as well as the need to preserve and develop the culture of the peoples. Trompenaars & Turner, (2006) analyzed the development process of modern Western society in terms of culture and cultural identity, pointing out that the gap is too far apart not only in poor countries, slow and developing, but

¹ The Fourth Industrial Revolution, 4IR, or Industry 4.0 (Bai et al., 2020) conceptualizes rapid change to technology, industries, and societal patterns and processes in the 21st

century due to increasing interconnectivity and smart automation. The term has been used widely in scientific literature (Colombo et al., 2014).

also in developed countries. These are oppression, exploitation, injustice, disparity between rich and poor, destruction and destruction of the environment.

Concerning the technology to culture, Akbari and Pishghadam, (2022) out that: "Technology plays a crucial role in fully understanding all aspects of language and uncovering the hidden patterns, such as sense and emotion density in texts" (In the study of culture, the authors argue that different cultural worldviews lead to different ways of life of the peoples of the East and the West, which refers to communicative culture; see, Konyratbayeva et al., 2021).

The work "Cultural preservation and cultural expression" by the author Salemink has focused on analyzing traditional culture and global culture, the ability to preserve and promote cultural heritage. Based on the works of Hobsbawm and Ranger (1983), the "invention of tradition", "construction of tradition". Salemink points out the principles and the relationship between culture and tradition (Salemink, 2002).

Huong, (2011) in the book on "Some theoretical and practical issues of building and developing Vietnamese culture" is a rigorous review summarizing articles published in journals on theory and practice of cultural construction and development. Vietnam in the process of international integration such as building an advanced Vietnamese culture imbued with national identity, comprehensive development, unity in diversity, deeply imbued with the spirit of humanity and democracy improvement; making culture closely linked and permeable to the entire social life, becoming a solid spiritual foundation, an important endogenous force for development.

Ha, (2011) in the book "Preserving the Vietnamese national identity in the current globalization context" has stated that: "The process of globalization is an inevitable and objective development trend of society, having a strong impact on economic and political life culture of all countries and peoples in the world. Globalization is making profound changes, from awareness to practice of all countries in all fields, within each country as well as in international relations. Globalization opens up many development opportunities, but also poses significant challenges for countries, especially for developing countries. One of the challenges that globalization poses is the fading and loss of national identity".

Along with the above approach, the author Nguyen Phu Trong in the work "Orientation for cultural development - the nation's endogenous strength in the conditions of market economy and international integration" has identified specific goals to 2020, vision to 2030: "Building the environment" healthy culture;

overcome and move towards repelling socio-cultural negatives and evils; Enhance national cultural potential; focus on developing human resources; Improve people's quality of life; improve Vietnam's human development index (HDI)" (Phu, 2014)

The Vietnamese value system from tradition to modernity and the road to the future has focused on academic concepts, methods, and theoretical tools about common cultural values. The book by Them (2016) also shows the good qualities of Vietnamese people such as: decency, optimism, cheerfulness, love of life, gratitude, respect for face, respect for women; At the same time, the author discusses "Changes of the traditional Vietnamese value system in the modern period", according to which in the face of rapid and drastic changes in space, time, social context, speed, etc. changes in the economy etc have made many "ugly" characteristics of Vietnamese people clearly revealed (Them, 2016).

Tri et al, (2021) have commented: "The Industrial Revolution 4.0 with its rapid development speed and profound impacts on all areas of the social life of each country, if left behind of this revolution, the backward development is also inevitable. On the contrary, if you make good use of the advantages of this revolution, the opportunities are huge" (where the article also analyses the impact of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 on educational culture).

Thus, the above works have clarified the nature and role of the industrial revolution 4.0, of culture. However, there are no works that present or analyse the impact of the industrial revolution 4.0 on cultural development in Vietnam. But the above works are documents for the author to clarify the research content.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This exploratory study aims to clarify the impacts of industrial revolution 4.0 on cultural development in Vietnam. Conceptually, there are many definitions of "culture": "Culturing is a blend of culture and language, implying that culture can be found in a language. Cultural genes (memes) can be discovered in a language and can be cured and improved if there is any problem with them. Further studies can check the effect of the revolution on culturing" (Akbari & Pishghadam, 2022). Or culture is "the living totality of human creative activities that have taken place in the past as well as are taking place in the present. Over the centuries, these creative activities have constituted a system of values, traditions, aesthetic tastes and lifestyles on which each nation asserts its own identity" (Le, 2001). It is an organic system of material and spiritual values created and accumulated by people through practical activities. To develop sustainably and stably, each country and nation must build

culture, design culture and people, link economic growth with cultural development, and stabilize socio-political stability.

Thus, culture is the totality of material and spiritual values created by people, accumulated in practical activities, and is a core element that creates the unique identity of a community society, it can dominate the psychological life and all activities of people living in that social community. Therefore, the process of awareness of the role and position of culture becomes an indispensable requirement to maintain, promote and orient the development of culture in accordance between tradition and modernity in today's conditions. To build and develop a culture in the context of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, while still ensuring modernity, in line with the country's reality (Tri & Nhe, 2020; Dung & Tri, 2021).

When studying culture, depending on the angle of approach in different aspects, culture can be classified into different fields. In the thesis, we approach two fields: *Material culture* is all achievements and products that people create in the process of material production, including architectural works, palaces, temples, pagodas, houses, tools, and instruments to serve and satisfy the needs of human life, against nature, against enemies, about food and accommodation, wear, travel, production methods, labor etc, are all aspects of culture. *Intangible culture* is the totality of spiritual values and achievements created by people in production and practical activities to satisfy the spiritual needs of the people. including politics, ideology, morality, lifestyle, customs, literature, art, science, education, beliefs, religion, festivals, mass media, etc. (for digital technologies and trends in cultural tangible and intangible heritage, see: Liritzis et al., 2015).

The country of Vietnam has experienced thousands of years of civilization and history, in the same years, the cultural and spiritual values of the Vietnamese community were cultivated and built during the struggle for national construction and defending the country of 54 ethnic groups on the S-shaped strip of land (Hang, 2022). The tangible and intangible cultural values of the Vietnamese ethnic community formed in history are the crystallization of the spirit of solidarity. The will to rise up of successive generations goes along with a rich and diverse working and living life. In the development process of history, there are cultural values from the past that are still associated with modern society and contribute to the driving force for economic and social development; but there are also ancient cultural achievements that have died out over time, or been transformed under the influence of society in the period of industrialization, modernization and modern life.

Looking at the history of the country, the Vietnamese community is divided into 54 different ethnic groups, the majority of which are Kinh people (Thanh & Binh, 2020, p.120).

There have been many legends about the origin of the ethnic groups in Vietnam such as the story "Bau Bea Mother" explaining the ethnic groups with the same origin; The story "Double Birds" lays hundreds and thousands of eggs that hatch into Kinh, Muong, Thai, Kh-mu, and Bana. The story of the Bana and Ede peoples tell that the Kinh and Montagnards are brothers of the same family; especially the story Lac Long Quan - Au Co gave birth to a bag of hundreds of eggs that hatched into hundreds of children, half followed their father to the sea to become Kinh, half followed their mother to the mountains to become ethnic minorities. King Hung is considered the common ancestor of the whole country (Chi, 2003, p.167). Traditional Vietnamese culture has also since been formed based on the characteristics and habits of each ethnic region and has the common characteristic of being based on agricultural culture, which is the product of a long historical process. from the beginning of the country's construction to the end of the 19th century (Tri, 2021, p. 84). In the process of being exposed to the natural and social environment, due to different geographical and climatic characteristics, the communities living in the territory of Vietnam have created cultural characteristics that, over time, have resulted in the development of different cultures. into the unique identity of each nation. That is reflected in the way of life, habits, ways of thinking, and behaving which have been maintained for many generations and still have a profound influence on the cultural and social life of Vietnam today (Chuong, 1999, p.163). Images of culture, cuisine, houses, customs, practices, festivals, religious beliefs, social organizations, literature, art, costumes of each ethnic group make up a whole. harmony, unity, and diversity in Vietnamese culture. Each ethnic group brings its own colors, its own nuances, all combined into a colorful picture of Vietnamese culture. Vietnamese culture is not simply cultural features according to common values for thousands of generations, it is a synthesis of cultural values from different regions, customs, and habits. For example, for the Vietnamese people from the past to the present, the Hung Kings are a sacred symbol of the nation, carrying the nation's unique cultural values, expressing the mind "towards the origin", "drinking water" country remembers its source", the spirit of national cohesion, creating great strength of the whole nation in the struggle against natural disasters and enemy sabotage. Saint Giong is a symbol containing the spiritual value of fighting

against foreign invaders and the strong will of the nation. Son Tinh is a symbol expressing the spiritual value of conquering nature and protecting and expanding the country. Meanwhile, the cultural values of Vietnam's ethnic minorities are cultural elements that are very vividly symbolized in religious activities, such as the Tay, Mo Muong, and the custom of eating buffaloes of some ethnic groups. ethnic minorities in the Central Highlands, the Kate festival of the Cham people... Cultural values are expressed through means of religious practice, such as altars, worship paintings, props, decorative arts, and symbols. votive papers, costumes, musical instruments, books of offerings, offerings, cuisine... crystallized in the forms of performance in service of beliefs, such as singing, dancing, music, expressed in sutras, teachings, rules, and regulations for the people who practice the ritual and the community as a whole (Son, 2022). Despite such differences, cultural values from national, regional, regional or ethnic approaches have unity in diversity, whereby the values of small communities always respect the value of the great community. The unity in this diversity of values has both created rich and attractive cultural nuances, contributing to the formation of "cultural assets", thereby creating advantages in socio-economic development associations of each region and region, while ensuring the stability of the national culture and the sustainable development of the country.

About language culture. In Vietnam, "Vietnamese" is the national language (national language) and all ethnic groups generally have their own language (mother tongue). In addition to the national language script (the written form of Vietnamese), our country has 26 ethnic minorities with their own scripts (such as Bana, Ede, Giarai, Cham, Khmer, Tay, Nung, Thai, and Mong). Every citizen in Vietnam, regardless of ethnicity, has the responsibility and the right to use

the national language in political, economic, cultural, and social activities... Only the basis of its use Fluency in the new national language helps to raise people's knowledge, expand access to information, and build a unified national-ethnic consciousness. Regarding the mother tongues of ethnic groups, Article 42, Chapter II of the 2013 Constitution affirms that citizens have the right to identify their ethnicity, use their mother tongue, and choose a communication language. Thus, respecting the mother tongue contributes to protecting the diversity of ethnic cultures (Giang, 2021)

Over the past time, along with the socio-economic development, the expansion of cultural exchange activities, the study, and use of the national language among the ethnic minorities in Vietnam have grown, and blindness has increased. letters are gradually rectified. Along with that, languages of ethnic groups are also respected, used, and preserved through teaching in some schools with a bilingual policy (teaching both the national language and the mother tongue of some ethnic groups).

At the same time, according to statistics, Vietnam has more than 40,000 relics inventory, of which over 36,000 relics are ranked provincial-level relics and over 3,000 relics are ranked national-level relics, there are over 20 relics. The relic is ranked as a special national relic, there are 08 Intangible Cultural Heritages recognized by UNESCO to be included in the Cultural Heritage of Humanity such as Hue royal court music, Central Highlands gong cultural space. There are dozens of tangible cultural heritages recognized by UNESCO as cultural heritages of the world such as Ha Long Bay, Ho Dynasty citadel, Quan Ho folk songs, Ca Tru folk songs, Xoan singing, Don ca tai tu in the South, Imperial Citadel of Thang Long Hanoi, Phong Nha Ke Bang Cave and some other monuments (Fig.1-4).

Figure 1. My Son Sanctuary (In 1999, My Son Sanctuary was selected by UNESCO as one of the modern and modern world heritages. (Source: <https://hutc.org/tai-nguyen/viet-nam-co-bao-nhieu-di-san-van-hoa-the-gioi-duoc-unesco-cong-nhan-ct32.html>)

Figure 2. Cultural space of gongs in the Central Highlands (The Central Highlands Gong cultural space was recognized by UNESCO as a Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Humanity on November 15, 2005. The cultural space of Gongs in the Central Highlands includes the following components: gongs, music played by gongs, people playing gongs, festivals using gongs (New Rice Celebration, Worshipping Ceremony Water wharf), the places where those festivals are held (long houses, communal houses, jail houses, fields, wharves, grave houses, forests next to the villages of the Central Highlands) (Source: <https://huttc.org/tai-nguyen/viet-nam-co-bao-nhieu-di-san-van-hoa-the-gioi-duoc-unesco-cong-nhan-ct32.html>)

Figure 3. Folk Songs - Quan họ Bắc Ninh (Quan Ho Bắc Ninh songs express the spirit, philosophy and local identity of the community in Bac Ninh. It helps forge social bonds within and between different villages). (Source: <https://bizivietnam.com/intangible-cultural-heritage-of-vietnam-by-unesco/>)

Figure 4. Gióng Festival of Phu Đổng and Sóc Temples (The Gióng festival of Phù Đổng and Sóc temples is celebrated annually in the outskirts of Hanoi. The festival is to honour the mythical hero, god and saint. Thánh Gióng or Saint Gióng was a legend who was believed to defend the country from foreign enemies using bamboo as weapon) (Source: <https://bizivietnam.com/intangible-cultural-heritage-of-vietnam-by-unesco/>).

Cultural change takes place due to many different effects in each period, historical period. In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, geographical distance is minimized. That means the exchange and relationship between people are expanded. Communities, peoples, and cultures come closer together. In each community, the culture and lifestyle of individuals are also influenced and influenced by each other. This interweaving directly contributes to the promotion of cultural diversity but also gives rise to a situation of cultural hybridization that makes the protection of identity in cultural diversity a difficult task for all countries ethnic.

In all fields, revolutions involve a fundamental, radical, profound, and radical change in the direction of progress. Industrial Revolution 4.0 has made knowledge capitalized, and penetrated deeply into material production, into every "novel" of human life, changing production forces and production relations export. This process takes place quickly in a short time and changes many cultural characteristics and lifestyles of people in many countries and ethnic groups, including Vietnam.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 The achievements and limitations of cultural development in Vietnam in recent years

In the process of international integration, the expansion, diversification, and multilateralization of foreign relations have created favorable conditions for promoting cultural exchanges between our country and other countries and territories around the world, of different sizes and levels. Many activities, such as Vietnamese culture day/week/month, art performance, cultural-tourism festival, film screening, book exhibitions, photos, cultural-art products, seminars, promotion, tourism promotion to introduce the image of the country and people of Vietnam are continuously held in many countries and territories around the world. External cultural and cultural exchange activities are chaired by the Ministry of Culture, Sports and Tourism, in collaboration with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and relevant ministries, branches and localities, mass media agencies, People's foreign affairs organizations, and Vietnamese embassies abroad have brought understanding, affection, friendliness, left a good impression on the international community, created premise and conditions for the international community, so that many countries and organizations around the world wish to actively promote exchanges and cooperation with Vietnam.

Figure 5. Hoi An Ancient Town (In 1999, Hoi An Ancient Town was recognized by UNESCO as a World Cultural Heritage) (Source: <https://toplist.vn/top-list/bai-van-thuyet-minh-ve-pho-co-hoi-an-lop-8-hay-nhat-45106.htm>)

At organizations, such as the United Nations World Tourism Organization, the International Folklore Foundation (IGF), the World Exhibition Organization, the International Intellectual Property Organization, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, United Nations Development Program, etc., the representative of Vietnam has shown dynamism and responsibility, contributed several recognized initiatives, contributing to the enhancement of the national position (Nasution et al., 2021; Dasih et al., 2019).

The policy of "socialization" of cultural activities has achieved practical results, initially mobilizing many resources in society. Socialization is considered one of the important solutions to attract social resources and economic sectors to participate in creative activities, provide and disseminate cultural products and build a community of the whole society in the cause of cultural development, creating conditions for cultural activities to develop strongly and widely, gradually raising the people's level of cultural enjoyment. The diversification of cultural subjects,

the transformation from the State's single-line resources for culture to the multi-dimensional, multi-component participation, synergies, and coordination from many different actors in society for cultural activities; promote diversity in types, ideas, trends, and

styles of cultural expressions, providing the public with richer spiritual food (Nasution et al., 2021; Dasih et al., 2019).

Figure 6. Ha Long Bay (UNESCO listed on the list of World Natural Heritage for the first time in 1994) (Source: <https://baochinhphu.vn/vinh-ha-long-duoc-binh-chon-vao-top-50-ky-quan-du-lich-thien-nhien-the-gioi-102275169.htm>)

Not only held abroad, but cultural agencies also actively coordinate to organize many international cultural exchange events and activities right in Vietnam, so that international organizations, diplomatic corps, writers, Culture, journalists, artists, entrepreneurs, and tourists can contact and interact with Vietnamese culture and people. Through many activities, Vietnam has gradually improved its cultural integration ability; effectively receiving cultural values, art, and modern, attractive, and typical expression methods of the world, enriching and elevating the form, content, and value of cultural products nation. Along with that is the establishment and operation of cultural institutions of many countries in Vietnam, such as the Goethe-Institut of Germany, the Library of the US Embassy's Cultural Office; cultural and linguistic centers of e.g. France, Japan, and Korea, creating favorable conditions for promoting cultural exchange activities of our country (Nyandra et al., 2018; Oviogun & Veerdee, 2020).

Cultural exchange activities have increasingly become a professional and effective channel, contributing to enhancing the position and image of the country and Vietnamese people in the international arena. Cultural exchange not only promotes relations with the foreign community but also spreads the country's culture to the overseas Vietnamese community, connects overseas Vietnamese with their homeland and country, and penetrates Vietnamese culture to the host country community.

However, besides the achieved results, the culture in Vietnam in the past time still has some limitations:

Firstly, the management mechanism is still mainly centralized; decentralization and decentralization are not high. The guidelines, guidelines, and plans for cultural development are largely determined and built from the macro level down to the micro level, not proposed and built from the bottom up, from the grassroots practice. Law has not yet become the ultimate tool to regulate, control, and regulate cultural life. Cultural awareness of branches and levels is sometimes still rigid, imposing, and dogmatic. The status of culture is still low, not put on par with other fields.

Secondly, economic development is not sustainable, which affects the development of all aspects of social life, including the field of culture (Loulanski and Loulanski, 2015)

Cultural institutions are still slow to innovate and lack synchronization. The legislation still has weaknesses. Some management documents that have just been issued have shortcomings, requiring adjustment and supplementation. The organization and implementation of legal documents on culture are still weak, so many legal regulations have not come to life. The implementation of many legal provisions related to culture is still confusing.

Thirdly, human resources for cultural development are weak and lack professional and management skills, especially innovation and business management skills. The quality of cultural management

staff at all levels does not keep up with the rich, diverse, and complex development of cultural activities, leading to confusion in policy-making and organizational guidance, violations of the law, and cultural policies.

Fourthly, investment in culture is not commensurate with the role and position of culture in development. In general, the level of investment in culture in the total budget expenditure is relatively low compared to other fields, not commensurate with reality, and uneven. The system of institutions and facilities for cultural activities is generally underdeveloped and in a state of deterioration, patchwork, lack of synchronization, and low efficiency.

Fifthly, the quality of services and cultural products is not high; there is also a lack of cultural brands at the national, regional, and international levels, and a lack of high-quality cultural products that contribute to soul nourishment, personality building, and moral education. The situation of import and trade deficit of foreign cultural products in Vietnam is superior to that of cultural exports, and the absorption of foreign cultural products is still lacking in selectivity. Vietnam's cultural products are still not creative and diverse, not meeting the needs of the public, and their competitiveness in the domestic and international markets is still low.

4.2 The impact of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 on the development of Vietnamese culture

The Industrial Revolution 4.0 has far-reaching effects on almost all areas of social life, not excluding the field of culture, as well as people - who are the subject objects of social relations is the embodiment of culture, the "identification" of each nation's culture. The results of the Fourth Industrial Revolution have had a strong impact on people's consumption trends, creating a big revolution in consumption concepts and habits. Thanks to the development of the internet, the birth of e-commerce has helped consumers choose and shop for goods online (sitting at home, choosing products around the world online; paying via accounts electronic accounts; receiving goods via delivery service). Through e-commerce, Vietnamese consumers have closer access to world commerce (Tri, 2021).

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commerce, Vietnamese consumers have closer access to world commerce (Lin et al., 2013).

The development of science - technology makes it possible for people to do many types of work by working remotely, not necessarily going to the head office or office, not having to communicate directly with colleagues and superiors, even with a partner and still get the job done. These are great benefits that science-technology brings, but this also makes people dependent on computers, smartphones, and internet systems, making people less interested in relationships in the community, society, and even family relationships... In the past, Vietnamese people's communication and behaviour were mainly through direct methods and were more discreet, delicate, formal, and even ritualistic, and sophisticated, but now, with speed and rhythm. Life is faster, people can communicate in many ways through the internet, such as using Zalo, Viber, Sky, Instagram, and Facebook. These technological achievements make people less likely to have problems communicating and act faster but at the same time inevitably more superficial (Navazesh & Kumar, 2008; Stock & Seliger, 2016).

Changing the standard cultural value system, creates a conflict between cultural values and traditional lifestyles with cultural values and modern lifestyles. The Industrial Revolution 4.0 creates a favourable basis for the strong cultural exchange process, and at the same time increases the conflict between many traditional and modern cultural factors and values when the old has not yet been lost and the new has not been clearly defined, not completely accepted by society.

The impact of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, several newly formed trends, cultural styles, and lifestyles have been controversial. It is a change in some conceptions and habits of a part of the people, from being heavy on love to rationality, from love to money; is the tendency to think that the family is no longer the center; the elements with material value partially replace the mental and emotional factors; is the formation of skepticism, denial of traditional cultural values and national history; is the moral deterioration, the degradation in social relations, especially the cognitive deviation, the lack of ideal living among a part of young people; is an increase in the generation gap in the perception of standard cultural values (Alaloul et al., 2020; Carvalho et al., 2018). The most common and easily recognizable expression in society is the non-cultural and unethical expressions that still exist quite commonly change, meanwhile, many beautiful acts and good deeds appear less and less, even in some cases become strange things in life. This partly reflects that the personality structure in each person has changed, leading to different trends in the perception of the standard cultural value system in social life.

However, the Industrial Revolution 4.0 also poses challenges for cultural development in Vietnam today, such as:

a) The Industrial Revolution 4.0 has strongly impacted all aspects of social life in most countries around the world, and Vietnam is no exception. Vietnam has a great opportunity to absorb values from many cultures but also faces the risk of losing its national cultural identity. The change in culture and lifestyle is inevitable, the problem is to direct that change in a positive direction; It is necessary to recognize and take advantage of the development of scientific and technological achievements as a favourable condition for the preservation, development, and dissemination of national cultural values to the world.

b) In the context of the strong development of multimedia and digital communication technology, the free market, and the cultural field needs to make a difference and apply scientific and technological advances in creating produce unique and diverse products and services to meet the needs of the public. The explosion of information and communication is accompanied by a wave of cultural interference and importation with many new cultural elements, which have positive aspects but also have many negatives, while the qualifications of staff and facilities techniques to manage these new problems are limited, leading to confusion and passivity in the implementation organization.

c) The decline in ethical culture, especially in the way of communication and behaviour, is also more and more evident in the industries that have traditionally carried the very good traditional values of the people like the education and health sectors. Much of the value in professional training and personal care today has disappeared and is replaced by a decline, a moral degradation that manifests itself through the public buying and selling of licenses, certificates, diplomas, and degrees granting all levels of education, buying and selling medical records, buying and selling health certificates, profiting from health insurance... The harms of moral and cultural deterioration in these fields are much more serious than the degradation in other areas because they are directly related to people, to the main resource, a kind of social capital that cannot be replaced in sustainable development (Tweed & Sutherland, 2007; Wegerif et al., 1999).

4.3 Some solutions to develop culture in the context of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 in Vietnam

The following proposed actions are deemed necessary:

a) organization is needed of the mastery and implementation of undertakings and policies on development, and strengthen the application capacity of scientific and technological achievements, on building an advanced Vietnamese culture imbued with national identity. Then, formulate an overall strategy for national science and technology development at the same time and in line with the socio-economic development strategy, in line with the orientation of preserving and promoting the national cultural identity;

b) Vietnamese culture must be placed in a dialectical relationship with all aspects of social life, especially with economic development. If only interested in economic development alone will form a pragmatic lifestyle of the consumer society; on the contrary, if only paying attention to cultural values, society will be poor, material life will be difficult, and spiritual life will be lacking. Therefore, it is necessary to regularly pay attention to building a culture in the economy, business culture, corporate culture, entrepreneurs with standards of honesty, respect for credibility, responsibility;

c) focus on building new lifestyles, and new cultural standards, building, developing, and creating new cultural values based on preserving and promoting traditional and inherited cultural values and promoting the diversity and cultural identity of ethnic groups, regions, and regions. Develop a mechanism to reasonably and harmoniously deal with the conservation, embellishment, and promotion of cultural heritage values, and historical and cultural relics with socio-economic development and education service traditional culture and tourism development. Directing cultural, educational, scientific, and technological activities toward the values of truth - goodness - beauty (Tri, 2022);

d) expand cultural exchanges, selectively accumulating the quintessence of human culture, good and beautiful lifestyles of the world's peoples, enriching the national culture; prevent and fight against harmful cultural penetration and countercultural lifestyles in the process of international integration. Actively cooperate in culture with other countries, diversify forms of foreign culture, deepen cultural external relations and achieve practical results;

e) there is a mechanism to train, attract, use, and implement satisfactory regimes and policies both economically and spiritually, to honour scientific researchers and cultural managers. In addition to investment from the state budget, it is necessary to socialize investment resources for culture, with specific financial mechanisms because this is an important and sensitive field and is the spiritual foundation of society. Increase investment in science-technology to study culture and people; and last, but not least, f) apply digital tools to develop Vietnamese archaeology

and cultural heritage for social, educational, sustainable-economic purposes (Tan, 2021; Liritzis and Korca 2019; Liritzis et al., 2016, 2020, 2021; Hatzopoulos et al., 2017; Haddad, et al., 2021).

5. CONCLUSION

In the context of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, building and developing culture must contribute to making each person not only aware of their rights, obligations, and responsibilities but also perform that responsibility in the best way in all areas of activities of social life, ensuring the country's sustainable development (Kuznets & Murphy, 1966; Tri, 2020). Taking

advantage of advantages, anticipating opportunities, and minimizing disadvantages before the challenges of Industry 4.0 for the development of Vietnamese culture in the coming years are very important for the overall development of the country. Taking advantage of opportunities and promoting strengths, limiting weaknesses, and overcoming challenges will be the best way for Vietnam to develop culture, truly turning culture into a driving force and goal for development. In order to make culture truly become the goal and driving force of sustainable development in the context of Industry 4.0, which is having a strong impact in all areas of social life (Cooper, 1993; Malterud, 2001).

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